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Impact of Education on Earnings in Ogun State: Economic Returns to Education

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Abstract: The doubt about the relevance of education in improving individual earnings has led to students' lack of interest in academic activities or not being interested in having additional qualifications. To determine if education is relevant to earnings, this study adopted a quantitative research method to determine if there is an economic return to investment in education in Ogun State. Three hundred eighty-five respondents were sampled for the study. Data analysis shows that education is among the major determinants, and an increase in the level of education leads to a rise in the individual's earnings. And the highest payoff in education is at the university level. The study recommends that the government prioritise financing education by providing scholarships and interest-free student loans.

Keywords: economic returns, education, employees, investment, higher education,

Introduction

The acquisition of education is important to the economic growth of any society. Pal (2023), Tao (2024), and Wei (2024) show that acquiring education enhances productivity, leading to higher earnings for individuals and economic development in society. Bah (2023) established a positive correlation between high literacy rates and increased per capita income. The high per capita income is attributed to the productivity gains associated with educational attainment. As such, societies with high literacy rates experience improved economic outcomes, greater individual earnings and enhanced economic growth (Patrinos & Psacharopoulos, 2020). The importance of education in achieving economic growth has led to supranational organisations advocating for and investing in the provision of education, especially among low and middle-income countries. Through Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG4), the United Nations has advocated for inclusive and equitable quality education to achieve sustainable development by 2030 (Ydo, 2022). To reduce poverty and bridge development gaps, the World Bank also invests in the provision of education among Sub-Saharan African countries (Mundy, 2019).

In Nigeria, the advocacy of supranational organisations and the realisation of the importance of education to economic development (Osisanwo et al. 2024). This advocacy has increased individual and government investment in education by establishing primary, secondary, and higher educational institutions. Universities, the highest academic institutions, are expected to be a base station for the contribution of education to the development of individuals and society. Wabike (2021) states that universities play dual roles in societies' economic development: they generate research and inventions that inform policy, process and practice and produce graduates with skills necessary for employment. By equipping graduates with the required knowledge and technical skills, universities prepare graduates to secure gainful employment, contribute to national productivity and increase their earnings. However, despite individual and societal investments in education, graduates face challenges in the labour market, including underemployment and low earnings, which has led to doubts about the private economic returns of investment in education (Olabiyi, 2021). This disconnect between educational attainment and employment opportunities has fuelled scepticism about acquiring formal education to improve earnings and economic returns for individuals.

The high rate of underemployment in Nigeria has led to low earnings for graduates, which has implications for economic development and social stability. Wayas et al. (2019) identified graduate underemployment as a social problem affecting the social fabric of Nigeria, linking it to rising rates of crime and criminality as unemployed and underemployed graduates may turn to illicit activities. This problem casts doubt on the expected economic returns to education, with Nigerians questioning whether education investments genuinely bring economic benefits for individuals. Alordiah et al. (2023) discuss the sentiment among Nigerian youths that "education is a scam," suggesting that formal education, especially at the university level, does not lead to economic prosperity. Instead, education is a colonial legacy imposing European systems and cultural practices irrelevant to Nigeria's economic development (Ojo et al., 2023). This disillusionment about the economic role of education to individuals has led to the declining pursuit of rigorous academic activity among students, deteriorating academic performance and fuelling social unrest in Nigerian schools.

To address the underemployment problem, the Nigerian government has introduced several employment generation programmes targeted at different levels of graduates; these programmes include the N-power programmes, Graduate Internship Scheme (GIS), YouWIN, National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) Skill Acquisition and Entrepreneurship Development (SAED) and National Directorate of Employment (NDE) skills acquisition programmes. Empirical studies, such as those by Eneji et al. (2020), also recommend vocational training, while Olabiyi (2021) advocated for the reinforcement of existing entrepreneurial education in Nigerian schools to alleviate the graduate underemployment crisis. Despite these policies and empirical interventions, the high underemployment rate among graduates in Nigeria persists (Olaiya et al, 2019). This situation reinforces the graduate belief that education does not benefit individuals economically. Hence, this study focuses on exploring the impact of education on individual earnings in Ogun State.

Literature review

Education is universally recognised as a form of investment in human capital that yields economic benefits and contributes to a country's future wealth by increasing the productivity capacity of its people. These economic returns to education are categorised into social economic returns --- economics returns to the society, and private economic returns---economic returns to individuals. Private economic returns to education are the financial benefits individuals derive from their investment in education, measured by earnings (Psacharopoulos, 2024). Private economic returns align with the belief that education improves productivity, leading to higher earnings (Becker, 1964a). In Nigeria, the perception that education leads to better earnings leads individuals to pursue further education. Onakoya (2017) argues that the belief in improved earnings led to the aspirational value individuals associated with formal education.

Empirical studies expose the economic benefits of education across different contexts. Bashir and Siddique (2023) believe that higher education levels improve individuals' employability and earning potential by enhancing their skills and competencies. However, labour market disparities, such as gender-based wage gaps, may limit the realisation of the economic benefit of education. Studies have shown earnings differences between males and females, with women earning less despite comparable qualifications (World Economic Forum, 2022). In a study conducted by Mincer (1974), individual income rose with age due to accumulated experience and skills. Also, the nature of employment—whether in the formal or informal sector—significantly affects the economic returns to education. Formal sector jobs, typically associated with higher wages and job security,

disproportionately reward educational qualifications compared to informal sector employment. Adedipupo and Onakoya (2019) and Montenegro & Patrinos (2014) demonstrated that education enhances human capital, leading to increased productivity and earnings. In Sub-Saharan Africa, Psacharopoulos and Patrinos (2004) found that returns to education are highest at the tertiary level, reflecting the demand for skilled labour in these economies.

Studies show that education correlates with earnings. Blundell et al. (1999) reported that university graduates in developed countries experience a significant earnings premium, further reinforcing the value of higher education. In Nigeria, several studies have explored the relationship between education and earnings. Ogundipe (2011) found that higher education yields economic returns, with graduates earning more than non-graduates. However, the persistence of graduate underemployment has raised questions about the reliability of private economic returns to investment in education. Olabiyi (2021) observed that many university graduates in Nigeria struggle to secure jobs, leading to widespread disillusionment with formal education. This issue is compounded by labour market mismatches, where graduates' skills do not align with employers' requirements.

Sectoral and regional differences may also complicate the assessment of education's economic returns. Public sector jobs in Nigeria often offer stable earnings but are less accessible due to limited openings and high competition. On the other hand, private sector employment often rewards skills and experience more generously but lacks the stability of public sector roles. Eneji et al. (2020) emphasised the importance of aligning educational curricula with labour market demands to bridge this gap and enhance employability. Despite these findings, some studies indicate that not all variables significantly impact earnings. For instance, the World Economic Forum (2022) found that gender disparities in earnings are less influential in specific regions and countries, potentially reflecting progress toward gender parity or gaps in data collection.

The human capital theory, developed by Becker (1964b) and Schultz (1961), and the dual labour market theory, proposed by Doeringer and Piore (1971), form the foundation of this study. The human capital theory posits that education enhances individuals' productivity, leading to higher earnings and contributing to economic growth. Becker (1964b) argued that investment in education yields long-term economic benefits, as it equips individuals with the skills and knowledge needed to perform effectively in the labour market. This human capital theory framework aligns with the study's focus on exploring the contribution of education to the earnings of individuals in different economic contexts in Ogun State (Onakoya, 2017). Despite the popularity of the human capital theory, it has faced criticism for its simplistic assumptions. Human capital theory sometimes overlooks structural earning factors such as labour market discrimination and socio-economic inequalities that influence earnings outcomes (Onakoya, 2017). For instance, unequal access to quality education can distort the relationship between educational attainment and earnings.

To balance the theoretical framework for this study, the human capital theory complemented by the dual labour market theory proposed by Doeringer and Piore (1971) was examined. The dual labour theory divides the labour market into primary and secondary sectors. Primary sector jobs offer higher earnings and stability, while secondary sector jobs provide limited economic returns. The dual labour market theory is relevant to Ogun State's labour market ecosystem, where the public sector represents the primary labour market, and the private sector is the secondary sector. Integrating the human capital theory and the dual labour market theory provides a holistic framework for analysing the private economic returns to education in Ogun State. This duopolistic

theoretical approach allows for a detailed examination of the private economic returns to education and the returns to investment in education in different economic sectors within the same geographical area. In tandem with the situations mentioned earlier, this study examines the nexus between educational attainment, labour market dynamics, and earnings determinants, with the aim of contributing to the discourse on the role of education in enhancing individual earnings aiming to offer insights that can inform policies aimed to maximise the economic benefits of education in Ogun State. Hence, this study focuses on exploring the impact of education on individual earnings in Ogun State. Specifically, the study examines the following questions:

1. What are the major determinants of earnings in Ogun State?
2. Does the level of education affect the variation in earnings in Ogun State?
3. What is the relationship between education and earnings of private and public sector employees in Ogun state?

Methodology

This study employed the descriptive survey research design to explore education's impact on individual earnings in Ogun State. The population for this study consisted of graduates of primary, secondary and tertiary institutions in Ogun State. The population of the study is unknown; as such, this study adopts the formula proposed by Cochran (1953), which is used to determine a sample size from an unknown population. The formula is as follows:

$$n = \frac{z^2 \times \rho \times q}{E^2}$$

Where:

n =required sample size

z^2 = z-score for the chosen confidence level

ρ = estimated proportion of the population (usually 0.5 for unknown populations)

$q = 1 - \rho$

E = margin of error.

Therefore, this study adopts a 95% confidence level ($z = 1.96$), ($\rho = 0.5$), and $E = 0.05$, the calculation would be:

$$n = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{0.05^2}$$

$$= 384.16$$

$$n = 385$$

With the mathematical determination of the sample size, this study adopted a sample size of 385.

A purposive sampling technique was used to choose seven (7) local government areas among the twenty (20) local government areas in Ogun State. The snowball sampling technique was used to select fifty-five (55) respondents from each of the sampled local government areas. Data collection was through the administration of a researcher-self-designed questionnaire tagged Economic Rate

of Returns to Education Questionnaire (E.R.R.E.Q.). The questionnaire was divided into three sections. Section A addresses the respondents' personal information, ranging from position to earnings, age, etc. Section B addresses the respondents' qualifications for experience and training. Section C addresses the respondent household information. The instrument was validated by ensuring the face and content validity. The developed instruments were given to two lecturers in the economics of education and one expert in educational evaluation to vet the structuring, adequacy and content validity of the items. Criticism and suggestions were used to produce the final copy of the questionnaire. The items on the questionnaire were related to the specific objective of the study, while its construct was to give sufficient information about the purpose of the research questions. To test the instrument's reliability, the researcher administered the instrument twice in two local government areas within Oyo State, which has an educational and labour market structure similar to Ogun State but in a different geographical location. This is done to determine the instrument's consistency using the test-retest method. The reliability coefficient was analysed using the Cronbach Alpha formula, and the results were found to be 0.83, respectively. This implied that the instrument was reliable.

In analysing the private economic rate of returns to education in Ogun state, data was retrained for individuals aged between 18 and 60. This age range was chosen based on contextual labour parameters in Ogun state. First, individuals aged 18 and above were included because, under Nigeria's education system, secondary education is officially expected to be completed by this age, and it is also the age when an individual, irrespective of his educational status, can seek formally paid employment in Ogun state. Secondly, the upper threshold of 60 years aligns with the prevailing retirement age in Ogun state. This approach excludes individuals who had not completed their education at the time of the study, thereby minimising potential measurement errors in constructing the education variable.

The Average Years of Schooling (AYS) metric was employed to derive the educational attainment variable (Edu) from the dataset. This process involved assigning specific numerical values to reflect the formal schooling years completed at various levels. These values approximate the level of educational stock and its contribution to an individual's human capital. Although this method, as shown in Table 1, the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) developed by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (2012)., modifications were introduced to capture partial completion of educational levels. For instance, individuals who completed only primary four or Junior Secondary School (JSS) 3 were assigned values corresponding to their actual years of schooling.

In the context of Ogun state, primary education spans six years, and secondary education an additional six years. Therefore, completing primary education was assigned a value of six, with lower values allocated proportionally based on incomplete schooling (e.g., primary two is assigned a value of 2, primary three value of 3, etc.). Similarly, completing lower secondary education (JSS3) was given a value of 9, upper secondary (Senior Secondary School) a value of 12, and post-secondary education, such as diploma qualifications, a value of 14. Further educational attainment was reflected as follows: Bachelor's degree certificates and equivalents were valued at 16.

Table 1: ISCED classification and the researcher's simplified version

ISCED CLASSIFICATION		NIGERIAN CLASSIFICATION		
Level	Stage of education	Level	Stage of education	Weight
1	Primary	1	Primary(P1-P6)	6
2	Lower secondary or second stage of basic education	2	Lower secondary (JS1-JS3)	9
3	Upper secondary	3	Upper Secondary (SS1-SS3)	12
4	Sub-Degree (Diploma)	4	Sub-Degree (Diploma/N.C.E.)	14
5	Degree	5	First Degree	16

Source: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (2012).

Furthermore, there are issues related to the data that was utilised in the analysis that require further clarification and justifications. Specifically, the ISCED classification extends to master's and PhD degrees; this study is restricted to holders of a bachelor's degree, which is the base university education expected to be acquired to reach the peak of a career in the public sector in Ogun state. On the measure of individual experience, an individual's potential experience (exp.) is computed as the person's age minus six years minus years of formal schooling, where the six years represents the period from birth to the starting age of formal schooling. To capture the return to different levels of education in Ogun State, a specification that decomposes years of schooling into variables for primary, secondary and tertiary attainments is estimated.

Data Analysis

Research Question One: What are the major determinants of earnings in Ogun State?

Table 2: Regression Summary showing the major determinants of earnings in Ogun State

Determinants	F-statistic	p-value	Remarks
Present occupation	32.393	.000	Significant
Nature of Job	2.501	.121	Not Significant
Age (years)	40.494	.000	Significant
Gender	0.589	.673	Not Significant
Educational Qualification	18.561	.000	Significant
Daily working hours	1.312	.109	Not Significant
Computer skills	3.690	.0591	Not Significant
Training	2.228	.113	Not Significant
Work experience	12.933	.000	Significant

Note. *Significant at .05 level

Table 2 shows the ANOVA regression summary with F-ratio and significance tests and their associated probabilities (*p*-value). The table shows four major determinants of earnings in Ogun State. Present occupation is a determinant of earning in Ogun state ($F = 32.393; p < .05$). Age also determines the earning profile in Ogun state ($F = 40.494; p < .05$). Educational qualification also determines the earning profile in Ogun state ($F = 18.561; p < .05$). The work experience of the also determines the earning profile in Ogun state ($F = 12.933; p < .05$). However, the nature of job ($F = 2.501; p > .05$), gender ($F = .589; p > .05$), daily working hours ($F = 1.312; p > .05$), skill of computer usage ($F = 3.690; p > .05$), and training acquired ($F = 2.228; p > .05$) were not determining factors to raising the earning profile in Ogun State.

Research Question Two: Does the level of education affect the variation in earnings in Ogun State?

Table 3: Effect of level of education on earning variation in Ogun State

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
1	Regression	601.135	1	601.135	18.561	.000
	Residual	12890.026	398	32.387		
	Total	13491.161	399			

Table 3 shows the effect of the level of education on the variation in earnings in Ogun State. The regression model revealed a differential in earnings among respondents based on their educational qualifications acquired, $F(1, 398) = 18.561, p < .0005$. This means that the level of education affects the variation in earnings among respondents in Ogun State. Figure 1 presents the mean rate of returns at different levels of education among respondents in Ogun State to show the variation in earnings.

Figure 1: Profile plots of mean earnings against educational qualification

Figure 1 illustrates the relationship between educational attainment and mean monthly earnings (in Nigerian Naira ₦); it shows that an increase in the level of education correlates positively with the average earnings of an individual in Ogun state. Individuals with only a First School Leaving Certificate (FSLC) have the lowest mean earnings of ₦70,000. While Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE) holders earn an average of ₦89,000 per month, this suggests that

secondary education provides improved access to job opportunities and earning potentials compared to FSLC certificate holders. The chart also shows that holders of diploma certificates (Ordinary National Diploma/ National Certificate in Education) earn an average of ₦99,000. Holders of Higher National Diploma (HND) earn monthly earnings of ₦115,000. This is an increase in comparison to holders of diploma certificates. Respondents with a university education, precisely a first degree, have been found to have the highest average monthly earnings, which is ₦133,000. This shows that while there is a positive relationship between an increase in the acquisition of education and average monthly earnings, the highest private economic returns to investment in education are at the university level. A comparison of the percentage increase in earnings in Ogun State is presented in Table 4

Table 4: Percentage differentials in monthly mean earnings across educational qualifications in Nigeria.

Educational Transition		Earnings Increase (₦)	Percentage Increase (%)
FLSC	→ SSCE	19,000	27.14
FLSC	→ Diploma	29,000	41.43
FLSC	→ HND	45,000	64.29
FLSC	→ Bachelor's degree	63,000	90.00
SSCE	→ Diploma	10,000	11.24
SSCE	→ HND	26,000	29.21
SSCE	→ Bachelor's degree	44,000	49.44
Diploma	→ HND	16,000	16.16
Diploma	→ Bachelor's degree	34,000	34.34
HND	→ Bachelor's degree	18,000	15.65

Table 4 shows that the transition from FSLC to SSCE yields a 27.1% increase in mean earnings, equivalent to ₦ 19,000 monthly increase. Earnings rise by 41.43% when individuals move from FSLC to Ordinary National Diploma/National Certificate in Education. The difference in earnings between holders of FLSC to that of HND is an average of ₦45,000 per month, which is 62.29%. The highest difference is between an FSLC holder and a bachelor's degree holder, estimated to be ₦63,000 per month, showing a differential percentage of 90.00%. The differential between the earnings of a diploma certificate holder and an SSCE holder is the lowest and stands at ₦10,000, which is 11.24% monthly. At the same time, SSCE to HND is ₦26,000, equivalent to 29.21%. SSCE and Bachelor's degree is ₦44,000, equivalent to 49.44%. For individuals with diploma certificates, the differential in earnings in relation to those with HND certificates is a monthly average of ₦16,000, which is 16.16%. This is lower than the differential between the earnings of a diploma certificate holder and a bachelor's degree holder, with a differential of ₦34,000, showing a 34.34% differential. Table 4 finally indicates that the lowest difference in earnings is between HND holders and Bachelor's degree holders, estimated to be a monthly average of ₦18,000, which is 15.65%.

Research Question Three: What is the relationship between education and earnings of private and public sector employees in Ogun state?

To estimate the relationship between education and earnings of private sector employees in Ogun State, the earnings of private sector employees (Y_a) were regressed on the explanatory variables (educational qualification, X_1 , present cadre, X_2 , age, X_3 , and work experience, X_4) of private sector employees.

Model Specification

The regression model employed specified earnings (proxy by an income index) as a function of educational qualification, present cadre, age, and work experience. While earnings are a dependent variable, educational qualification, present cadre, age, and work experience are explanatory variables. Thus, this study's methodological approach will follow the Mincerian estimation technique specification, which specifies the private economic rate of returns as a function of educational qualification, present cadre, age, and work experience.

Micerian earning function takes the form:

$$\ln W_i = \alpha + \beta S + \gamma_1 EX_i + \gamma_2 EX_i^2 + \epsilon_i$$

Thus, the model can be specified as stated below:

$$Y_a = (X_1 + X_2 + X_3 + X_4 + \epsilon_i) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

wq

In a linear form, the model can be specified as;

$$Y_a = b_0 + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 + b_4 X_4 + \epsilon_i \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$\ln Y_a = \beta_0 + \ln \beta_1 X_1 + \ln \beta_2 X_2 + \ln \beta_3 X_3 + \ln \beta_4 X_4 + \epsilon_i \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Table 5: Relationship between education and earnings of private sector employees with other earning determinants

Dependent Variable: Earnings of private sector employees
 Method: Least Squares
 Included Observations: 244

Explanatory Variable	Coefficients	Standard Error	t-statistic	Prob.
Constant	-28.68089	0.548670	0.123857	.5227
Log(X1)	5.167957	0.593497	0.102072	.0126
Log(X2)	0.060579	11.57763	0.359824	.2196
Log(X3)	-4.165906	44.15668	-0.649525	.1224
Log(X4)	0.057829	0.834822	0.234532	.0534

R-squared = 0.574554 Adjusted R-squared = 0.440279

F-statistics= 0.677336 S.E of Regression = 1.157555

Durbin-Watson stat. = 1.0.009717 Prob. (F-statistic) = 0.057519

$$Y_t = -28.68089 + 5.167957X_1 - 0.060579X_2 - 4.165906X_3 + 0.057829X_4$$

The result, as contained in Table 5, revealed that while educational qualifications are positively related to the earnings of private sector employees, age is inversely related to the earnings of

private sector employees and is found to be insignificant. The positive sign of the educational qualification indicates that an increase in education of private sector employees will increase the earning profile of the private sector employees by 5.167957. The coefficient of multiple determination shows that the model is of good fit, with approximately 57% of earnings being explained by the variables included in the model, while the remaining 43% are factors influencing private economic rate of returns but were not captured in the model. Similarly, the low Durbin-Watson value of 0.009717 suggests the presence of serial correlation. Besides, only the educational qualification was found to be statistically significant at a 5 per cent significance level, while others were not when considered individually. The relationship between education and earnings of private sector employees is further depicted with a line graph in Figure 2

Figure 2: Line graph showing the relationship between education and earning profile of private sector employees in Ogun State

In order to estimate the relationship between education and earnings of public sector employees in Ogun State, the earnings of public sector employees (Y_p) were regressed on the explanatory variables (educational qualification, X_1 , present cadre, X_2 , age, X_3 , and work experience, X_4) of public sector employees.

Model Specification

Micerian earning function takes the form:

$$\ln W_i = \alpha + \beta S + \gamma_1 EX_i + \gamma_2 EX_i^2 + \epsilon_i$$

Thus, the model can be specified as stated below:

$$Y_p = (X_1 + X_2 + X_3 + X_4 + \epsilon_i) \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

In a linear form, the model can be specified as;

$$Y_p = b_0 + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 + b_4 X_4 + \epsilon_i \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

$$\ln Y_p = \beta_0 + \ln \beta_1 X_1 + \ln \beta_2 X_2 + \ln \beta_3 X_3 + \ln \beta_4 X_4 + \epsilon_i \dots \dots \dots (6)$$

Table 6: Relationship between education and earnings of public sector employees with other earning determinants

Dependent Variable: Earnings of public sector employees
 Method: Least Squares
 Included Observations: 141

Explanatory Variable	Coefficients	Standard Error	t-statistic	Prob.
Constant	14.25378	2.6785	0.73211	.0000
Log(X1)	11.34156	0.75432	0.21831	.0000
Log(X2)	2.87390	0.64832	0.98321	.0167
Log(X3)	1.27812	0.27315	0.57832	.0327
Log(X4)	0.98215	0.92351	0.62183	.0721

R-squared = 0.81813 Adjusted R-squared = 0.80184

F-statistics= 4.3215 S.E of Regression = 0.27821

Durbin-Watson stat. = 1.910 Prob. (F-statistic) = 0.046211

$$Y_t = 14.25378 + 11.34156 X_1 - 2.87390 X_2 - 1.27812 X_3 + 0.98215 X_4$$

The result, as contained in Table 6, revealed that educational qualifications are highly and positively related to the earnings of public sector employees. Present cadre, age and work experience were also found to be positively related to earnings of public sector employees and were found to be insignificant except for work experience ($p > .05$). The positive sign of the educational qualification indicates that an increase in education of public sector employees will increase the earning profile of the public sector employees by 11.34156. The coefficient of multiple determination shows that the model is of high good fit, with approximately 82% of earnings being explained by the variables included in the model, while the remaining 18% are factors influencing private economic rate of returns but were not captured in the model. The relationship between education and earnings of public sector employees is further depicted with a line graph in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Line graph showing the relationship between education and earning profile of public sector employees in Ogun State

Discussion Of Findings

This study focuses on the impact of education on individual earnings in Ogun State. The analysis of data collected concerning question one revealed that present occupation significantly determined earnings among individuals in Ogun State. This finding is consistent with the human capital theory, which posits that a person's job reflects their skills, knowledge, and productivity, directly influencing their earnings (Becker, 1964a). For example, entrepreneurial jobs typically command higher earnings due to other variables like risks and investment involved. Age was also found to be a significant determinant of earnings in Ogun State; this supports the Mincer earning functions, which suggests that income rises with age due to accumulated experience and skills (Mincer, 1974). Young workers may earn less due to limited professional exposure, while older workers benefit from enhanced expertise and seniority. However, in some contexts, this pattern can decline at advanced ages due to a potential decrease in productivity and health.

The findings also show that educational qualification is a significant determinant of earnings in Ogun State. These findings align with empirical evidence suggesting a positive correlation between education and earnings, as higher educational attainment often equips individuals with higher skills necessary to secure better-paying jobs (Psacharopoulos & Patrinos, 2004). Apart from these variables, the study found that work experience also has a significant positive impact on individual earnings in Ogun State. These findings also support the arguments that accumulated work experience enhances human capital by improving job performance and increasing productivity (Blundell et al., 1999). In Ogun State, these findings may reflect the value employers place on highly experienced workers with institutional knowledge and professional networks of a specific industry.

Interestingly, gender and job nature were not significant determinants of earnings in Ogun State. These findings deviate from the global trends, where gender disparities often affect wage differentials (World Economic Forum, 2022). In Ogun State, this could suggest either progress towards gender parity or limitations in the data's ability to capture latent inequities. Other insignificant variables to determining earnings in Ogun state, are daily working hours, computer skills and training acquired. These findings suggest that these variables may contribute to individual productivity but are not directly monitored in Ogun State's current labour market structure. Summarily, present occupation, age, educational qualification, and work experience are the major determinants of earnings in Ogun State. This aligns with existing literature on income determinants. However, variables such as the nature of the job, gender, daily working hours, computer skills, and training acquired did not significantly affect individual earnings in Ogun State.

The analysis of research question two, which sought to determine the variation in earnings with the level of education in Ogun State, revealed that education significantly affects earnings, supporting the human capital theory. This study's findings align with Ogundipe (2011), who asserts that education consistently yields positive economic returns across various situations. In Ogun State, individuals with higher education levels, such as university degrees, earn more than those with lower qualifications. For instance, attaining a university degree gives a monthly average of ninety per cent higher monthly earnings than an FSLC holder. The findings show that for each level of education attained, there is a guaranteed increase in the accrued monthly earnings. This finding aligns with Schultz's (1961), Montenegro & Patrinos's (2014) and Pscharapoulos (2024). The implication is that in Ogun state, the higher the education level attained by an individual, the

higher their monthly average earnings would be compared to someone with a lower level of education and assuming in the same labour market ecosystem.

The analysis of research question three states that '*what is the relationship between education and earnings of private and public sector employees in Ogun State?*' revealed exciting findings and new understandings of complex phenomena of private economic rate of returns to education. It was found that education has a positive and statistically significant relationship with the earnings of private and public sector employees in Ogun state. However, education has a more substantial effect in determining earnings in the public sector. The private sector also shows increased earnings growth with increased education, aligning with the human capital theory (Becker,1964a). The public sector's more substantial influence on education in determining earnings stems from the reliance on educational qualifications for structured career progression and remuneration, which aligns with the civil service rules in Ogun State. This also aligns with Psacharopoulos and Patrinos' (2004) findings on the role of education in earning disparities. The disparities may also stem from the public sector's standardised pay structure and promotion criteria (Montenegro & Patrinos, 2014). In contrast, private sector earnings are influenced by unmeasured factors, such as firm-specific policies and market dynamics, showing more variable and less structured remuneration practices.

The findings also show the differences in the significance of other determinants like cadre, age, and work experience. These factors are more influential in determining earnings in the public sector, where work experience impacts earnings, showing the public sector's dual emphasis on education and tenure (Schultz,1961). On the other hand, the private sector relies on educational qualifications and productivity, with other variables being insignificant.

In summary, acquiring education positively affects earnings, regardless of the economic sector. However, sectoral structure and rules make a difference in how significantly they affect employees' earnings.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study's findings show that education is among the significant earnings determinants in Ogun State. An increase in the level of education leads to a rise in earnings for an individual. This means there is an economic return on investment in education. The study further concludes that education contributes to earnings for both private-sector and public-sector employees in Ogun state. Although the contribution to earnings is more profound in the public sector than in the private sector, as such, the study recommends that government and policymakers should prioritise expanding access to quality university education to maximise the economic benefits of educational attainment. This can be done by awarding scholarships, zero-interest student loans, and partnerships with private institutions that can facilitate this goal, especially for the underprivileged population. Educational institutions should also strengthen the alignment between curricula and labour market demands. This can be achieved by integrating vocational and technical skills training, particularly for first-school leaving certificate and senior school certificate holders. This would assist them in improving their earnings in the labour market. Employers, whether in the private or public sector, should incentivise their employees to seek additional education while in their service to boost the organisation's productivity.

Suggestion for further findings

This study suggests that empirical findings extended to the relationship between education and earnings should include additional sectors, such as informal employment and entrepreneurship, which were not covered in this study. This would provide a more comprehensive understanding of how education impacts earnings across the different economic sectors of Ogun State. A longitudinal study should also be conducted to track individuals over time and provide deeper insights into how education impacts earnings growth, career progression, and job stability. This study would allow researchers to capture the long-term benefits of education and identify potential lags in economic returns. Given that skills acquisition and training were statistically insignificant in this study, further research could investigate the effectiveness of different training programmes, their alignment with labour market needs, and their impact on earnings. Also, the study can delve into the role of the acquisition of digital skills on earnings.

References

- Adedipupo M.B & Onakoya T.S. (2019). Private economic rate of investment to education among teaching staff in Ogun State teaching service commission. *International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 7, 47-49.
- Alordiah, C., Omumu, F., & Omenebele, K. V. (2023). Investigating why students in Nigeria perceive education as a scam. *Journal of Applied Learning & Teaching*, 6(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37074/jalt.2023.6.1.31>
- Bah, I.A. (2023). The relationship between education and economic growth: A cross-country analysis. *Research, Society and Development*, 12(5), 1-13.
- Bashir, A., & Siddique, Z. (2023). Appraising the lifetime private economic returns of postgraduate degrees: Evidence from Pakistan. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10(1), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-01565-6>
- Becker, G. S. (1964a). *Human capital*. Columbia University Press.
- Becker, G. S. (1964b). *Human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis, with special reference to education*. University of Chicago Press.
- Blundell, R., Dearden, L., Meghir, C., & Sianesi, B. (1999). Human capital investment: The returns from education and training to the individual, the firm, and the economy. *Fiscal Studies*, 20(1), 1–23.
- Cochran, W. G. (1953). *Sampling techniques*. John Wiley.
- Doeringer, P. B., & Piore, M. J. (1971). *Internal labor markets and manpower analysis*. Lexington, MA: D. C. Heath and Co.
- Eneji, R. I., Nwagbara, E. N., & Kati, G. (2020). Entrepreneurship training for mitigating unemployment in Nigeria: How have the tertiary institutions fared? *Journal of Social Economics Research*, 7(1), 42–50. <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.35.2020.71.42.50>
- Mincer, J. (1974). *Schooling, experience, and earnings*. Columbia University Press.
- Montenegro, C. E., & Patrinos, H. A. (2014). *Comparable estimates of returns to schooling around the world*. World Bank.

- Mundy, K. (2019). Facing forward, looking back? The world bank's new report on basic education in sub-saharan Africa. *Comparative Education Review*, 63, 281 - 287.
- Ogundipe, M.A. (2011). *An introduction to economics of education*. Tunigraphics Press.
- Ojo O.T., Babalola A.T. & Omotosho B.J. (2023) Decolonizing Nigerian educational system as an impetus for a holistic development, *British Journal of Education*, 11 (9), 1-15
- Olabiyi, O. B. (2021). Education and the paradox of graduate unemployment and employability in Nigeria. *Electronic Journal of Social and Strategic Studies*, 2(1), 112-123. <https://doi.org/10.47362/EJSSS.2021.2114>
- Olaiya S., Onakoya T.S. & Adeyemi R. I. (2019). Drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions in South-West, Nigeria. *Journal of Social Issues*, 4, 28-33.
- Onakoya, T. (2017). *Assessment of private economic rate of return to investment in education among staff of Ogun State Local Government Service Commission (Master's dissertation, Tai Solarin University of Education)*. Department of Educational Management.
- Osisanwo, B.G., Babasanya, A. O., Okutimiren, A. O., & Daniel, T. T. (2024). Strategic investment in education: A catalyst for accelerated economic growth in Nigeria. *Economic Insights –Trends and Challenges*, 13(1), 85-95.
- Pal, L. C. (2023). Impact of education on economic development. *Khazanah Pendidikan Islam*, 5(1), 10–19. <https://doi.org/10.15575/kp.v5i1.25199>
- Patrinos, H. A., & Psacharopoulos, G. (2020). Returns to education in developing countries. In S. Bradley & C. Green (Eds.), *The economics of education* (2nd ed., pp. 53–64). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-815391-8.00004-5>
- Psacharopoulos, G. (2024). Returns to education: A brief history and an assessment. *Education Economics*, 32(5), 561–565.
- Psacharopoulos, G., & Patrinos, H. A. (2004). Returns to investment in education: A further update. *Education Economics*, 12(2), 111–134.
- Schultz, T.W. (1961). Investment in human capital. *American Economic Review*, 51, 1-17.
- Tao, X. (2024). An examination of education's economic influence from a family perspective. *Highlights in Business, Economics and Management EMFRM 2023*, 24, 2324–2328.
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. (2012). *International Standard Classification of Education: ISCED 2011*. UNESCO Institute for Statistics. <https://uis.unesco.org/sites/default/files/documents/international-standard-classification-of-education-isced-2011-en.pdf>
- Wabike, P. (2021). University role in liaising partners for society development: A case study of a university contribution to society development through the liaising social partners in Ghana. *Journal of Educational Issues*, 7(2), 18–37.
- Wayas, G. G., Selvadurai, S., & Awang, A. H. (2019). An examination of the causes of unemployment among youths in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, 8(12S2), 567–573.

Wei, Y. (2024). The role of education in economic advancement: A case study of Silicon Valley. Highlights in Business, Economics and Management EMFRM 2023, 24, 2046–2052.

World Economic Forum. (2022). Global Gender Gap Report.

Ydo, Y. (2022). Reaching SDG 4: Our shared responsibility and renewed commitment to action. Prospects, 52, 223–229.